

GL MICAVE

D1.2 GLOMICAVE Semantic Model

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2020 GA No. 952908
Project title	Global Omic Data Integration on Animal, Vegetal and Environment Sectors
Duration of the project	1 st November 2020 - 30 th April 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP1: Integration and harmonisation of multi-omics data Task 1.1: Task 1.2. Common data model for harmonizing omic data
Document due Date:	31/07/2021
Actual date of delivery	31/07/2021
Leader of this deliverable	FZJ
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	FINAL

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
X	19/07/2021	FZJ	Draft version circulated to partners
X	31/07/2021	FZJ	Final report

Executive summary

The GLOMICAVE Semantic Model performs a key role within the GLOMICAVE platform, providing a uniform structure for the description of experimental datasets sourced from various primary repositories across the omics domains. This metadata is automatically retrieved from the primary repositories and converted into standardized representation. The primary purpose of this metadata is to enable the downstream automated analysis and interpretation of the experimental datasets, using both traditional statistical and machine learning based approaches. In addition, this metadata can be used as a data index, allowing the user to more efficiently identify and reuse relevant datasets for large scale analyses. This semantic model will be a live document that will be extended from this first version and throughout the work package, being updated in line with the evolution of the project.

GLOMICAVE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 952908.

This document is the sole responsibility of the consortium and reflects only the consortium view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Union.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information sheet.....	2
Executive summary	2
Table of contents	3
1. Introduction.....	5
1.1 The Role of Metadata.....	5
1.2 Challenges.....	5
1.3 GLOMICAVE Metadata Strategy	6
1.4 Scope	6
2. Analysis of Existing Data Exchange Models, Semantic Models and Standards.....	6
2.1 Analysis of Existing Metadata Model Standards	6
2.1.1 Genomics	6
2.1.2 Transcriptomics	7
2.1.3 Proteomics.....	7
2.1.4 Metabolomics	8
2.1.5 Multi-Omics.....	8
2.2 Analysis of Metadata Models in Repositories	8
2.2.1 European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)	8
2.2.2 ArrayExpress	9
2.2.3 Sequence Read Archive (SRA).....	9
2.2.4 Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO)	9
2.2.5 PRIDE.....	9
2.2.6 MassIVE	10
2.2.7 Metabolights	10
2.2.8 National Metabolomics Data Repository (NMDR).....	10
2.3 Analysis of Relevant Ontologies	10
2.4 Analysis of Taxonomies	11
2.5 Gap Analysis	11
3. Metadata Model and Ontology Construction.....	12
3.1 The ISA metadata model.....	12
3.2 Use Cases	13
3.2.1 Pregnancy and calving outcomes in cattle	13
3.2.2 Meat quality	13
3.2.3 Fruit quality management.....	13
3.2.4 Plant growth:.....	14
3.2.5 P-removal and recovery	14
3.2.6 Bioenergy production	14
3.3 Requirements	15

4. Evaluation and validation of the approach	16
4.1 Evaluation Criteria	16
4.2 Validation.....	17
5. ANNEXES	18
5.1 Table 1A: ENA Checklist - Default sample (ERC000011)	18
5.2 Table 1B: ENA Checklist - Crop Plant Sample (ERC000035)	19
5.3 Table 1C: ENA Checklist - Plant Sample (ERC000037)	20
5.4 Table 1D: ENA Checklist - GSC MixS wastewater sludge (ERC000023)	23
5.5 Table 1E: ENA Checklist - GSC MixS host associated (ERC000013)	26
5.6 Table 1F: ENA Checklist - GSC MixS plant associated (ERC000020)	29
5.7 Table 2A: ISA Configuration - Genome Sequencing.....	32
5.8 Table 2B: ISA Configuration – Metagenome Sequencing	33
5.9 Table 2C: ISA Configuration – Transcriptome Sequencing	34
5.10 Table 2D: ISA Configuration – DNA Methylation Sequencing	35
5.11 Table 2E: ISA Configuration – Proteomics Profiling	36
5.12 Table 2F: ISA Configuration – Mass Spectrometry based Metabolomics	37
5.13 Table 2G: ISA Configuration – Nuclear Magnetic Resonance based Metabolomics.....	38

1. Introduction

1.1 The Role of Metadata

Metadata has an important but often under-appreciated role in life sciences, providing an essential contextual bridge between the traditional scientific output, published academic literature, and the large associated datasets needed to support, validate and potentially help reproduce the scientific conclusions.

Due to their substantial data storage requirements, these large datasets are not stored by the academic journals themselves, e.g., as supplementary material, but stored in one or more dedicated data repositories. Journals generally enforce a requirement that these datasets are submitted to and made available from such a repository when the paper is published, and that the necessary location / identifiers be provided within the paper text to allow readers to retrieve the datasets if they desire.

The process of submitting data into these repositories requires the population of associated metadata, providing some level of formalized description. This is generally stored alongside the datasets within a data repository, and traditionally, its primary purpose has been organisational, by linking these datasets back to the published academic literature which they support and to the individuals / organisations who created them.

The second purpose of metadata has been dataset discovery for re-use. Given the costs of generating e.g., large sequencing datasets, it is unsurprising that most funding agencies are keen to promote such re-use. Most repositories thus support not only the retrieval of datasets by identifiers (which can be obtained from the corresponding published paper), but also by text keyword search and increasingly by structured metadata criteria related to the source material (i.e., genotype), experimental treatment classifications (e.g., heat stress), sample processing procedure (Poly-A selection), assay technology (Illumina HiSeq 2000) etc.

Another potential purpose of metadata, for which it has been traditionally under-used, is to assist data analysis and integration, in a semi or fully automated manner. This generally requires a much more structured representation of the experimental details, precisely defining the source material for each biological entity, their growth environment including any treatments. It should also cover the samples taken and their subsequent processing and measurement procedures, all of which may impact the downstream analysis and/or interpretation of the data. Important experimental concepts such as replication should also be apparent, implicitly or explicitly, from this metadata.

1.2 Challenges

The major issue preventing the effective use of metadata in life sciences has been sheer diversity of experimental scenarios within the field, which continues to broaden with time. Except for the organisational aspects, which are close to universally applicable, almost every facet of metadata is relevant only to a small subset of scientific endeavours. As a result, it has been a massive ongoing challenge to formalize an appropriate structure which captures the necessary experimental attributes, and in general it has been necessary to use flexible approaches such as free-text descriptions, or user-defined attributes. However, while these approaches are tolerable for human interpretation, neither are suitable for automated consumption.

A secondary issue is that those who make their data available via repositories are also responsible for creating the accompanying metadata. However, they derive relatively little or no value from this metadata themselves. This has the understandable result that the minimum efforts are often exerted, sufficient only to meet the repository enforced requirements, and often

resulting in incomplete and/or inaccurate metadata in the repositories or selecting which repository to use to minimise the metadata creation burden.

1.3 GLOMICAVE Metadata Strategy

As a platform which integrates data from multiple repositories, in as automated manner as possible, the broad diversity and often questionable quality of metadata in source repositories is a definite challenge. The requirement to combine data from multiple different omics inherently means dealing with a much broader and more complex range of metadata than any individual repository.

In addition to the typical concerns around dataset discovery, data integration places additional demands on the metadata, since the datasets from multiple source repositories need to be correctly reconciled based on common or otherwise equivalent samples, biological entities etc. It is clearly necessary to allow these critical aspects of metadata to be manually curated as part of the data import / integration process.

However, despite the importance of metadata to GLOMICAVE's data integration goals, it is not realistic to require every user to fully audit and potentially populate any and all missing metadata in every dataset they import from other repositories. As such, all but the most essential metadata must be considered as optional by the system.

1.4 Scope

Given the multi-source integration approach of the GLOMICAVE project and the need for reconciliation/curation of the imported metadata, it is apparent that the experimental metadata will exist in two versions, namely the original form, which will be kept verbatim as imported from the source repository, and the integrated form, which will connect the various biological subjects, samples etc from the disparate repositories, and enable holistic analysis. This latter form may also contain curated additions, e.g., based on literature, if the original repository lacks the necessary details.

Beyond the experimental metadata, the GLOMICAVE platform will require organisational metadata, to organise datasets into a project hierarchy, manage data sharing between users and/or organisations etc. The details of such organisational metadata are outside of the scope of this deliverable.

2. Analysis of Existing Data Exchange Models, Semantic Models and Standards

2.1 Analysis of Existing Metadata Model Standards

The so-called 'Minimum Information' standards are the main drivers of standardized metadata, with specific standards developed for each of the Omics, under the Minimum Information for Biological and Biomedical Investigations (MIBBI) umbrella. The Minimum Information standards themselves only provide an abstract data model however, so in order to be applied in practice, an associated standard specifying one or more file formats

2.1.1 Genomics

Targeted single-organism genome sequencing, as opposed to meta-genomic or epi-genomic sequencing, requires limited experimental metadata, since the genome sequence is independent of growth conditions and experimental treatments. The most important information

is clearly the origin of the sequence, namely the species, isolate, accession etc, which is ideally connected to a species taxonomy or other standardized identifier system. A field indicating sex, ploidy, mating type etc, may also be relevant, depending on the species. Beyond these sample characteristics, detailed technical metadata providing a description of the sequencing process, the processing pipeline(s) and the analysed data is beneficial. These various aspects, both sample related and technical, are described in the Minimum Information about a Genome Sequence (MIGS) standard.¹

Metagenomic datasets are inherently more complex, containing a mixture of full and/or partial genomic sequences from multiple, generally unknown organisms. They can be sampled from various sources, be it a host-independent environment e.g. marine, soil, wastewater etc or association with a specific host, be it human, animal or plant. Depending on the experiment, metadata on monitored conditions such as temperature, pH and salinity may be available. In addition, for controlled environments and some host-associated experiments, metadata on experimental treatments may be crucial. The Minimum Information about a Metagenome Sequence (MIMS)² is the main standard in this area, although the Minimum Information about a Metagenome Assembled Genome (MIMAG)³ and ...about a Single Amplified Genome (MISAG)⁴ may also be relevant. These 3 standards, along with the MIGS standard above, are coordinated within the Minimum Information about Any Sequence (MIxS)⁵ family.

Epigenetics refers to additional information related to DNA molecules beyond their canonical base sequence, such as DNA methylation or the presence/absence of proteins / histones etc. These can be assayed by various techniques which selectively enrich/deplete regions of DNA, which is then sequenced on a suitable high-throughput DNA sequencing platform. This data can then be processed to produce a quantitative signal, conceptually similar to that from RNA-Seq. Since epigenetic signals are transient and condition dependent, they require comprehensive descriptions of experimental treatments, which is also similar to RNA sequencing. As a result of these commonalities, epigenetic datasets typically follow the same Minimum Information about a Sequence Experiment (MINSEQE)⁶ standard as RNA sequencing experiments.

2.1.2 Transcriptomics

The measurement of transcripts on micro-arrays was the first widely applied high-throughput technology in biology, enabling the abundance of thousands of transcripts in a single experiment. This was a conceptual revolution since experimental results were no longer limited to helping to answer a single biological question for the original investigator but could potentially be re-used and integrated with other datasets to answer additional questions later. It is unsurprising therefore, as the first technology to illustrate the potential of data reuse and integration, micro-array-based transcriptomics also inspired the first Minimum Information standard, namely Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment (MIAME).⁷ Later, as high throughput sequencing of RNA (RNA-Seq) replaced microarrays as the technology of choice, a corresponding standard, Minimum Information about a Sequencing Experiment (MINSEQE).

2.1.3 Proteomics

Continual improvements in protein measurement techniques, particularly in mass spectrometry, have enabled high-throughput proteomics experiments which are now capable of measuring 1,000s of protein abundances within a single assay. Although this is not quite at the same scale

¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2409278/>

² <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18479204/>

³ <https://www.nature.com/articles/nbt.3893>

⁴ <https://www.nature.com/articles/nbt.3893>

⁵ <https://gensc.org/mixs/>

⁶ http://fged.org/site_media/pdf/MINSEQE_1.0.pdf

⁷ <https://www.nature.com/articles/ng1201-365>

as available in transcriptomics, it is nonetheless sufficient to justify data reuse. However, the diversity of sample preparation and measurement techniques in the field means that the resulting Minimum Information About a Proteomics Experiment (MIAPE)⁸ standard is quite broad, and covers not only the modern mass spectrometry based approaches, but also older techniques like gel electrophoresis and protein/peptide micro-arrays.

2.1.4 Metabolomics

Due to the wide variety of molecules involved, metabolomics requires a diverse set of measurement technologies, with both mass spectrometer and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) platforms commonly used. An additional challenge in metabolomics is the molecule identification, and where this is not possible, robust approaches allowing datasets with unknown metabolites to be analysed and compared. These aspects are codified in the Minimum Information About a Metabolomics experiment (MIAMET)⁹ standard.

2.1.5 Multi-Omics

The various Minimum Information standards covered so far are strongly linked to their omics domain due to their detailed description of the sample preparation techniques and details of the measurement platform. However, except for genomics, all of these standards must include a description of the origin of the biological samples, their growth conditions and experimental treatments, which are not inherently platform dependent, but vary across different biological domains, e.g., bacteria, fungi, plant or animal. Furthermore, the rise in multi-omics experiments, where a single sample is assayed using e.g., transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics approaches, had motivated the separation of the 'biological growth' aspects of the experiment from the 'assay' parts. The Reporting Structure for Biological Investigation (RSBI)¹⁰ metadata model was the result of restructuring metadata away from the earlier measurement-platform centric approaches, towards a more modular approach combining an appropriate description of the biological material with one or more platform-specific assay descriptions. The central role of the Investigation, Study and Assay concepts led to the naming of this model as ISA, and naming of the related tabular format as ISA-TAB.¹¹

2.2 Analysis of Metadata Models in Repositories

The creation of appropriate metadata standards is only the first step towards data-reuse. Unsurprisingly, ensuring these standards are adopted by the community and actually used appropriately to describe datasets is a much bigger challenge. The primary arenas for this are the data repositories themselves, not just in terms of enabling standard-compliant metadata to be stored, but also, encouraging and perhaps enforcing it as part of the submission process. However, it is clear that creating complete and accurate metadata represents a considerable burden on data submitters, and some of the repositories have understandably decided against enforcing strict metadata standards as part of the data submission. As a result, surveys have consistently found that metadata standards in major repositories is of variable quality at best.¹²

2.2.1 European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)

The ENA database, operated by the EBI, is comprehensive, with almost universal submission of all published sequence datasets to it or one of its peer repositories (which are then mirrored within the ENA). Submission to one of these repositories is generally enforced as part of the

⁸ <https://www.nature.com/articles/nbt1329>

⁹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S136013850400175X>

¹⁰ <http://archive.fged.org/mged/Workgroups/rsbi/RSBIPaperOMICS06.pdf>

¹¹ <https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/pdf/10.1089/omi.2008.0019>

¹² <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201921>

publication of literature. Technical metadata, such as library preparation details, sequence enrichment and sequencing platform are captured consistently. However, the situation regarding experimental metadata is somewhat more liberal, presumably due to the wide range of scenarios within its scope, which have distinct requirements.

The ENA submission process requires the selection of a ‘sample checklist’, which defines a set of attributes for each submitted sample. However, it is up to the submitter to select the appropriate checklist, and often the simpler ‘default’ checklist is used when a more appropriate and more detailed option exists. Furthermore, many fields are optional within each checklist and/or allow arbitrary text to be entered, resulting in incomplete or difficult to interpret metadata.

2.2.2 ArrayExpress

ArrayExpress, which is operated by the EBI, was originally designed for microarray based experiments, but also includes sequencing-derived quantitative datasets, in transcriptomics and epigenomics. It is however a much smaller database than the ENA, containing only approximately 75k projects and 2.6M datasets at the time of writing.

The ArrayExpress submission process places a stronger emphasis on describing the experimental metadata. Historically this was implemented by uploading metadata using the Investigation Description Format (IDF) and Sample Data Relationship Format (SDRF) formats, which are part of MAGE-TAB, designed to support MIAME-compliant metadata. Due to the challenges involved in creating these files, Annotare, a web-based tool for creating these files during submission was developed.

This strong metadata focus of ArrayExpress is likely due to historical roots as a molecular phenotypic database. It also encourages, but doesn’t absolutely enforce, the use of separated attribute fields rather than textual descriptions. In some cases, the ArrayExpress has also served as a gateway to submit sequencing data to the ENA, and in these cases, the detail level of the metadata in the ArrayExpress records can be superior to that in the ENA.

2.2.3 Sequence Read Archive (SRA)

The SRA database, which is the NCBI-operated peer of the ENA, is regularly synchronized with the ENA. It is unsurprising therefore that it has a similar content profile, with comprehensive datasets accompanied by relatively strong technical metadata, but notably weaker experimental metadata.

2.2.4 Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO)

The GEO database is the NCBI operated equivalent of ArrayExpress, originally designed for microarray datasets, but increasingly used for sequence-derived quantitative datasets. Unlike the ENA-SRA data replication approach, data is not automatically synchronized between ArrayExpress and GEO.

While experimental metadata in GEO aims to be MIAME/MINSEQE compliant, there is relatively little enforced structure with user-defined key-value pairs commonly used to supply additional metadata attributes. Analysis has shown¹³ that these additional metadata terms are commonly but inconsistently used, making automated interpretation challenging.

2.2.5 PRIDE

The EBI’s PRIDE database was originally designed as a repository for raw Mass Spectrometry spectra from proteomics experiments and is thus somewhat analogous to the ENA. It has a

¹³ <https://bmcbioinformatics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12859-017-1832-4>

strong focus on technical metadata, with only high-level experimental metadata fields like Organism, Organism Part and Disease within the core datasets attributes. Detailed experimental metadata representation using the SDRF format is supported and encouraged, but not enforced. As a result, less than 1% (129 of 14042) datasets on PRIDE include highly detailed metadata, based on the provided 'annotated' search feature.

2.2.6 *MassIVE*

The MassIVE proteomics database, operated by the University of California, San Diego, has a similar strong focus on raw spectra and technical metadata, rather than experimental metadata. As a result, many datasets appear to lack structured experimental metadata entirely while some include it in an ad-hoc spreadsheet format. Overall, less than 4% (386 of 11,425) of the experiments within MassIVE are returned when filtering for 'study design'.

2.2.7 *Metabolights*

The Metabolights database is a relatively modern repository for metabolite data. It offers not only raw MS and NMR spectra storage with their related technical metadata, but also puts a strong emphasis on experimental metadata, requiring the use of ISA-TAB metadata formats for all submissions. Although the database size is relatively small, with only 842 public datasets, the comprehensive approach to metadata means that a large proportion of these datasets should be amenable to automated integration.

2.2.8 *National Metabolomics Data Repository (NMDR)*

The NMDR is a metabolomics repository hosted by the University of California, San Diego. Similarly to Metabolights, the NMDR datasets have a strong emphasis on experimental metadata, although it uses a custom mwTab format, which makes the database highly suitable for integration. However, it is also somewhat limited in size, with only 1518 publicly available experiments.

2.3 Analysis of Relevant Ontologies

One of the key issues with data integration is the inconsistent use of attribute terms and units between different experiments. This can impact molecular phenotypes (e.g. units for a transcription abundance estimate or metabolite concentration), macro phenotypes (e.g. is 'fruit weight' measured in grams or kilograms), and experimental metadata (affecting treatments, environmental conditions, sampling etc). To eliminate this ambiguity, it is strongly encouraged that attributes reference appropriate terms from an ontology to provide an unambiguous description of the specific attribute / unit being used.

Potential ontologies which can be used for this purpose include:

- Experimental Factor Ontology: <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/>
- Ontology for Biomedical Investigations: <http://obi-ontology.org/>
- Plant Ontology: <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-ontology>
- Plant experimental conditions ontology: <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-experimental-conditions-ontology>
- Plant stress Ontology: <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-stress-ontology>
- Anatomy: <https://github.com/obophenotype/human-developmental-anatomy-ontology/>
- Mammalian phenotypes: <https://github.com/obophenotype/mammalian-phenotype-ontology>

2.4 Analysis of Taxonomies

The NCBI Taxonomy (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>) is a curated hierarchical classification and nomenclature of all organisms referenced from the various NCBI sequence databases. It represents the broadly accepted hierarchical classification of these organisms, although by necessity, includes lineages with uncertain placement within the structure. The use of NCBI taxonomy identifiers for species and lineages is almost universal within the various repositories, with the obvious exception of environmental / metagenomic samples, for which this information is not known.

The GTDB taxonomy (<https://gtdb.ecogenomic.org/>) is an effort to generate a more complete taxonomy for bacteria and archaea using an automated classification pipeline. As a result of this automation, it is rapidly able to incorporate newly sequenced genomes, and therefore serves as a valuable resource for classifying genomes assembled from metagenomic datasets.

2.5 Gap Analysis

Despite the substantial efforts invested in standardizing experimental metadata made to date, between formal standardization efforts such as the various Minimum Information proposals on one hand, and the efforts of the various repositories on the other, there are still substantial gaps around experimental metadata to be resolved. These gaps are particularly notable in the proteomics repositories, where the majority of datasets appear to lack any detailed experimental metadata. This is also a problem in the sequencing data repositories (ENA and SRA), where despite the existence of suitable 'checklists' for various sample classes, notably those in the environmental and plant domains, many datasets omit relevant attributes or describe key experimental properties using custom key-value pairs.

Although this problem is broadly recognised, it is not simple to solve at source. As a result, GLOMICAVE needs to be able to handle missing (and potentially incorrect) metadata when data is imported.

3. Metadata Model and Ontology Construction

Since the ISA framework offers the most developed and established multi-omics metadata model, it is logical to adopt its design philosophy as a starting point for GLOMICAVE.

3.1 The ISA metadata model

Figure 1: The main entities and relationships within the ISA metadata model.¹⁴

While a full description of the ISA model is out-of-scope for this document, a brief outline in this context may be useful. The entities of the ISA model and their relationships are shown in **Figure 1** above.

The main entities in the ISA model are, not surprisingly, the Investigation, the Study and the Assay. The top-level Investigation Entity serves primarily as a container for one or more Studies. Both Investigations and individual Studies can be linked to people, organisations and publications. Studies represent a coherent unit of experimental work with a shared study design and set of experimental factors and describe the biological subjects of this work. Studies also contain one or more Assays, which focus on the measurement process, related to the biological subjects in the study. Assays are limited to describing a particular kind of measurement using a

¹⁴ <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.11.13.382119v2>

particular measurement technology, and thus multi-omics studies will always feature multiple assays.

3.2 Use Cases

The GLOMICAVE industrial uses include two from each sector, animal, plant and environmental, with various omics relevant for each.

3.2.1 *Pregnancy and calving outcomes in cattle*

This task aims to identify the biomarkers predictive of pregnancy and calving outcomes in cattle

Datasets include:

- Metabolomics: embryo culture and recipient blood plasma
- Proteomics: recipient blood plasma
- Phenomics: Outcome, calving conditions, calf health and body measurements
- Genomics: Genetics of recipient

Metadata include:

- Sample Timepoint: 0 or 7 day
- Other Time factors: hour / season of collection, time from collection to storage
- Temperature: body, environmental and sample storage temperatures
- Herd: Location and social factors (dominance)
- Feeding: pasture based and intensive, use of specific foods
- Recipient: body condition; reproductive history and milk production records

3.2.2 *Meat quality*

This task aims to connect key meat quality factors to their underlying genetic and molecular phenotype characteristics, as well as feeding conditions (grass vs grain).

Datasets include:

- Genomics: Whole-genome sequencing datasets to determine genetic variation
- Epigenomics: Whole genome bisulphate sequencing to determine DNA methylation
- Transcriptomics: RNA-Seq to relate gene expression to feed and phenotype
- Metabolomics: Profiling of muscle metabolome
- Phenomics: Assessment of Longissimus Dorsi muscle including pH, Water Holding Capacity, Chemical composition (proteins, fat, water, minerals and vitamins), tenderness (Warner Bratzler test), colour, sensory evaluation and oxidative state

Metadata include:

- Feeding: Grain vs Grass fed

3.2.3 *Fruit quality management*

This task aims to gather the remaining multi-omics development time-series datasets for 10 commercially relevant fruit species (some datasets exist already), as well as a multi-omics peach dataset comparing healthy and virus infected plants, to enable a comprehensive multi-species, multi-omics analysis

Datasets include:

- Transcriptomics: Fruit time series for 10 species and infected vs healthy peach
- Proteomics: Fruit time series for 10 species
- Metabolomics: Fruit time series for 10 species and infected vs healthy peach
- Phenomics: Fruit traits, including organoleptic properties, shape, colour and climacteric character

Metadata include:

- Species
- Fruit Development Stage / Timepoint
- Infection status

3.2.4 Plant growth:

Datasets include:

- Genomics: Variant data for 585 genotypes
- Transcriptomics: RNA-Seq time-series with multiple tissue types and genotypes
- Phenomics: Whole plant phenotypes and root development timing

Metadata include:

- Genotype
- Timepoint
- Tissue type

3.2.5 P-removal and recovery

This task aims to integrate data on microbial conversions in relation to biological P-removal by linking metagenomics, metatranscriptomics and metabolomics data to full-scale observations on P transformations and bioenergy production.

Datasets include:

- Genomics: Long and short read metagenomic datasets
- Transcriptomics: High resolution time-series
- Metabolomics: High resolution time-series
- Monitored Attributes: Chemical parameters e.g., pH

Metadata include:

- Primary state: anerobic, denitrifying or aerobic

3.2.6 Bioenergy production

This task aims to integrate meta-genomics and meta-transcriptomics data obtained from full scale anaerobic digesters with operational data, in both standard and co-digestion approaches.

Datasets include:

- Genomics: Meta-genomics datasets from long and short read sequencing
- Transcriptomics: Meta-transcriptomics datasets
- Monitored Attributes: Treatment efficiencies, quality of the digestate and methane production

Metadata include:

- Co-digestion factors

3.3 Requirements

In keeping with the ISA approach, we break down the experimental details into the source material, growth treatment & conditions, sampling, sample processing and measurement areas, with one or more nodes for each of these stages.

The ISA model allows all of these aspects to be extensible; however, the specific attributes and types should follow established standards as far as possible.

- Bio Source: The WP6 use-cases have clearly distinct requirements in this regard.
 - The animal use cases involve tracking individuals, and presumably parent-offspring relations, in addition to genotype.
 - Plant use-cases need only track sources at the genotype level, since the specific plants are generally grown from pooled seed stocks.
 - The environmental use-cases need the ability to specify metagenomic mixtures which are broadly consistent, though not fully specified.

In the plant/animal cases, the genotype would (ultimately) reference a taxonomy such as the NCBI taxonomy: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

The GTDB (<https://gtdb.ecogenomic.org/>) may provide a more useful ontology for bacteria in the environmental use case, but is probably more relevant at the data analysis stage.

- Growth Process: It is required to clearly specify the treatment vs control conditions during growth. Beyond that, it not yet determined how detailed these attributes need to be, although the guideline of accepting all existing metadata and permitting optional enhancement should apply.

Monitored attributes, such as temperature, methane production etc are implemented as assays linked directly to the growth process, without any intermediate sampling.

Relevant ontologies in this area:

- Experimental Factor Ontology: <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/>
- Ontology for Biomedical Investigations: <http://obi-ontology.org/>
- Plant Ontology: <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-ontology>
- Plant experimental conditions ontology: <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-experimental-conditions-ontology>
- Plant stress Ontology: <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-stress-ontology>
- Sampling: In the case of animal / plant use-cases, the sampling is almost always described as specific tissue type, area, etc.

Relevant Ontologies are:

- Experimental Factor Ontology: <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/>
- Plant Ontology: <https://github.com/Planteome/plant-ontology>
- Anatomy: <https://github.com/obophenotype/human-developmental-anatomy-ontology/>
- Mammalian phenotypes: <https://github.com/obophenotype/mammalian-phenotype-ontology>

For all use-cases, the sampling timeline is an additional important attribute.

- Sample processing: The ISA model has the concept of protocols and protocol parameters, which appears sufficient for most if not all use cases.
- Measurement: These vary based on the particular type of omics and measurement technology rather than animal/plant/environment category. The ISA provides a baseline set of attributes for each of the main omics, known as ISA configurations (<https://github.com/ISA-tools/Configuration-Files>), which are based on the corresponding “Minimum Information” standards.

There are specific ontologies for each measurement technology, including:

- RNA Sequencing: <https://kim.bio.upenn.edu/software/ornaseq.shtml>
- Mass spectrometry: <https://www.psidev.info/groups/controlled-vocabularies>

There are also ontologies describing the data produced:

- Gene Ontology – Transcripts / Proteins: <http://geneontology.org/>
 - Proteins: <http://www.obofoundry.org/ontology/pr.html>
 - Chebi: Small molecules determined by metabolomics: <http://www.obofoundry.org/ontology/chebi.html>
 - Phenotype and Trait Ontology: <https://github.com/pato-ontology/pato/>
- Data Processing: This includes early processing e.g., base calling of sequence data from raw signals, or later processing such as alignment against a reference genome annotation.

4. Evaluation and validation of the approach

4.1 Evaluation Criteria

To validate the potential to apply the ISA framework to the task of metadata integration within GLOMICAVE, the following criteria must be satisfied:

- It must be possible to create (potentially incomplete) ISA entities from the metadata records in the various repositories in a manner which captures as much of that metadata as possible in a largely automated manner.
- It must be possible to merge metadata records from different datasets, possibly created from different primary repositories, into unified ISA entities which represent these multi-omics datasets as they actually were performed. As part of this process, it is necessary to reconcile e.g., different subject or sample IDs which actually refer to the same biological entities / materials. Since the knowledge of which datasets, subjects and samples in different repositories are, in fact, related is likely to exist only in literature form, this process is expected to be user guided.
- It must be possible for the user to curate this metadata, and using additional knowledge e.g. from literature, to further correct and/or refine the metadata to more accurately reflect the experiment as performed.

4.2 Validation

- The automated conversion of metadata from various repositories into ISA format has already been validated, at least as a proof of concept, within prior work.¹⁵ It is likely however, that some additional development work will be needed to ensure this functionality can be reliably integrated within GLOMICAVE, and to ensure any recent changes to repository metadata can be incorporated.
- The ability to merge studies, by concatenating their contained sources, samples and assays is inherent to the structure of the ISA model, due to its use of 1:N relationships at each level required. Likewise, the use of a graph-based representation of the experimental process from source/subject, to sample, to measurement means that entities can be freely shared to accurately reflect the real-world process. However, it is clear that this will require substantial development work, as the current ISA API does not include entity merge modification operations of this type.
- Extending the ISA API to enable incremental insert/update/delete operations represents additional development work but represents functionality that would be necessary regardless of the underlying model chosen. There are no known reasons why basing the GLOMICAVE metadata model on the ISA framework negatively impacts this goal.

¹⁵ <https://isatools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/importdata.html>

5. ANNEXES

5.1 Table 1A: ENA Checklist - Default sample (ERC000011)

Field Name	Field Format	Requirement	Units
cell_type	free text	optional	
dev_stage	free text	optional	
germline	free text	optional	
tissue_lib	free text	optional	
tissue_type	free text	optional	
collection_date	restricted text	optional	
isolation_source	free text	optional	
lat_lon	free text	optional	
collected_by	free text	optional	
geographic location (country and/or sea)	text choice	optional	
geographic location (region and locality)	free text	optional	
identified_by	free text	optional	
environmental_sample	text choice	optional	
mating_type	free text	optional	
sex	free text	optional	
lab_host	free text	optional	
host scientific name	free text	optional	
bio_material	free text	optional	
culture_collection	free text	optional	
specimen_voucher	free text	optional	
cultivar	free text	optional	
ecotype	free text	optional	
isolate	free text	optional	
sub_species	free text	optional	
variety	free text	optional	
sub_strain	free text	optional	
cell_line	free text	optional	
serotype	free text	optional	
serovar	free text	optional	
strain	free text	optional	

5.2 Table 1B: ENA Checklist - Crop Plant Sample (ERC000035)

Field Name	Field Format	Requirement	Units
cell_type	free text	optional	
dev_stage	free text	optional	
organism part	free text	optional	
ploidy	free text	optional	
infect	free text	optional	
protocol	free text	optional	
sampling time point	free text	optional	
initial time point	free text	optional	
growth condition	free text	optional	
genotype	free text	recommended	
sex	free text	optional	
age	free text	recommended	
genetic modification	free text	optional	
phenotype	free text	optional	
cellular component	free text	optional	
individual	free text	optional	
disease staging	free text	optional	
immunoprecipitate	free text	optional	
replicate	free text	optional	
cultivar	free text	optional	
ecotype	free text	optional	
cell_line	free text	optional	
strain	free text	optional	
time	free text	optional	
dose	free text	optional	
chemical compound	free text	optional	
experimental factor 1	text choice	optional	
experimental factor 2	text choice	optional	
experimental factor 3	text choice	optional	
experimental factor 4	text choice	optional	
experimental factor 5	text choice	optional	
block	free text	optional	
environmental stress	free text	optional	
environmental history	free text	optional	

5.3 Table 1C: ENA Checklist - Plant Sample (ERC000037)

Field Name	Field Format	Requirement	Units
ploidy	free text	recommended	
number of replicons	restricted text	recommended	
extrachromosomal elements	restricted text	optional	
estimated size	restricted text	recommended	mL,g,mg,ng
sample volume or weight for DNA extraction	restricted text	optional	
collected_by	free text	optional	
collection date	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (altitude)	restricted text	optional	M
geographic location (country and/or sea)	text choice	mandatory	
geographic location (latitude)	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (longitude)	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (region and locality)	free text	optional	
identified_by	free text	optional	
geographic location (depth)	restricted text	optional	m
environment (biome)	free text	optional	
environment (feature)	free text	optional	
geographic location (elevation)	restricted text	optional	m
source material identifiers	free text	recommended	
sample collection device or method	free text	optional	
sample material processing	free text	optional	
isolation and growth condition	free text	mandatory	
propagation	free text	recommended	
amount or size of sample collected	restricted text	optional	L,g,kg,m2,m3
sample storage duration	restricted text	optional	hr,day,wk,mth,yr
sample storage temperature	restricted text	optional	°C
sample storage location	free text	optional	
sampling time point	free text	optional	
plant structure	free text	mandatory	
plant developmental stage	free text	mandatory	
sampled age	free text	optional	
sample phenotype	free text	optional	
sample health state	text choice	recommended	
sample disease status	free text	recommended	
sample disease stage	free text	optional	
sample wet mass	free text	optional	

sample dry mass	free text	optional	
sample height	free text	optional	
sample length	free text	optional	
growth facility	text choice	recommended	
sample capture status	text choice	optional	
genotype	free text	optional	
genetic modification	free text	optional	
organism common name	free text	recommended	
subspecific genetic lineage rank	free text	recommended	
subspecific genetic lineage name	free text	recommended	
biological status	free text	optional	
organism phenotype	free text	optional	
ancestral data	free text	optional	
source material description	free text	optional	
biotic relationship	free text	optional	
growth habit	text choice	optional	
plant sex	free text	optional	
climate environment	free text	optional	
gaseous environment	free text	optional	
seasonal environment	free text	optional	
soil_taxonomic/FAO classification	free text	recommended	
soil_taxonomic/local classification	free text	optional	
soil_taxonomic/local classification method	free text	optional	
soil type	text choice	optional	
soil type method	free text	optional	
drainage classification	text choice	optional	
texture	free text	optional	% sand silt clay
texture method	free text	optional	
soil water content	free text	optional	
soil pH	free text	recommended	
plant growth medium	free text	mandatory	
rooting conditions	free text	recommended	
culture rooting medium	free text	recommended	
rooting medium macronutrients	free text	recommended	
rooting medium micronutrients	free text	recommended	
rooting medium organic supplements	free text	recommended	
rooting medium carbon	free text	recommended	
rooting medium regulators	free text	recommended	
rooting medium solidifier	free text	recommended	
rooting medium pH	free text	recommended	
air temperature regimen	free text	recommended	
antibiotic regimen	free text	optional	

chemical mutagen	free text	optional	
fertilizer regimen	free text	optional	
fungicide regimen	free text	optional	
gravity	free text	optional	
growth hormone regimen	free text	optional	
herbicide regimen	free text	optional	
humidity regimen	free text	optional	
mineral nutrient regimen	free text	recommended	
non-mineral nutrient regimen	free text	optional	
pesticide regimen	free text	optional	
pH regimen	free text	optional	
radiation regimen	free text	optional	
rainfall regimen	free text	optional	
salt regimen	free text	optional	
standing water regimen	free text	optional	
watering regimen	free text	recommended	
water temperature regimen	free text	optional	
plant treatment	free text	recommended	
light regimen	free text	recommended	
biotic regimen	free text	optional	
mechanical damage	free text	optional	
chemical administration	free text	optional	
perturbation	free text	optional	

5.4 Table 1D: ENA Checklist - GSC MixS wastewater sludge (ERC000023)

Field Name	Field Format	Requirement	Units
project name	free text	mandatory	
experimental factor	free text	optional	
ploidy	free text	optional	
number of replicons	restricted text	optional	
extrachromosomal elements	restricted text	optional	
estimated size	restricted text	optional	
reference for biomaterial	free text	optional	
finishing strategy	free text	optional	
annotation source	free text	optional	
sample volume or weight for DNA extraction	restricted text	optional	mL,g,mg,ng
nucleic acid extraction	free text	optional	
nucleic acid amplification	free text	optional	
library size	restricted text	optional	
library reads sequenced	restricted text	optional	
library construction method	free text	optional	
library vector	free text	optional	
library screening strategy	free text	optional	
target gene	free text	optional	
target subfragment	free text	optional	
pcr primers	free text	optional	
multiplex identifiers	free text	optional	
adapters	free text	optional	
pcr conditions	free text	optional	
sequencing method	free text	mandatory	
sequence quality check	text choice	optional	
chimera check	free text	optional	
relevant electronic resources	free text	optional	
relevant standard operating procedures	free text	optional	
investigation type	text choice	mandatory	
collection date	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (country and/or sea)	text choice	mandatory	
geographic location (latitude)	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (longitude)	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (region and locality)	free text	optional	
wastewater/sludge environmental package	text choice	mandatory	
geographic location	restricted text	optional	m

(depth)			
environment (biome)	free text	mandatory	
environment (feature)	free text	mandatory	
environment (material)	free text	mandatory	
source material identifiers	free text	optional	
sample collection device or method	free text	optional	
sample material processing	free text	optional	
isolation and growth condition	free text	optional	
propagation	free text	optional	
amount or size of sample collected	restricted text	optional	L,g,kg,m2,m3
oxygenation status of sample	text choice	optional	
organism count	free text	optional	
sample storage duration	restricted text	optional	hr,day,wk,mth,yr
sample storage temperature	restricted text	optional	°C
sample storage location	free text	optional	
biochemical oxygen demand	restricted text	optional	mg/L (5 days@20C)
chemical oxygen demand	restricted text	optional	mg/L (5 days@20C)
pre-treatment	free text	optional	
primary treatment	free text	optional	
reactor type	free text	optional	
secondary treatment	free text	optional	
sludge retention time	restricted text	optional	hr,day,wk,mth
tertiary treatment	free text	optional	
specific host	free text	optional	
health or disease status of specific host	free text	optional	
alkalinity	restricted text	optional	mEq/L
industrial effluent percent	restricted text	optional	%
sewage type	free text	optional	
wastewater type	free text	optional	
temperature	restricted text	optional	°C
pH	restricted text	optional	
efficiency percent	restricted text	optional	%
emulsions	restricted text	optional	g/L,ng/L,µg/L
gaseous substances	restricted text	optional	µmol/L
inorganic particles	restricted text	optional	mg/L,mol/L
organic particles	restricted text	optional	g/L
sample salinity	restricted text	optional	psu
soluble inorganic material	restricted text	optional	g/L,mol/L,ppm
soluble organic material	restricted text	optional	g/L,mol/L,ppm
suspended solids	restricted text	optional	g/L,mol/L,ppm
total phosphate	restricted text	optional	µg/L,µmol/L
nitrate	restricted text	optional	µmol/L

phosphate	restricted text	optional	μmol/L
sodium	restricted text	optional	μmol/L,ppm
total nitrogen	restricted text	optional	μg/L,μmol/L
miscellaneous parameter	free text	optional	
subspecific genetic lineage	free text	optional	
trophic level	text choice	optional	
relationship to oxygen	text choice	optional	
known pathogenicity	free text	optional	
encoded traits	free text	optional	
observed biotic relationship	text choice	optional	
chemical administration	free text	optional	
perturbation	free text	optional	

5.5 Table 1E: ENA Checklist - GSC MixS host associated (ERC00013)

Field Name	Field Format	Requirement	Units
project name	free text	mandatory	
experimental factor	free text	optional	
ploidy	free text	optional	
number of replicons	restricted text	optional	
extrachromosomal elements	restricted text	optional	
estimated size	restricted text	optional	
reference for biomaterial	free text	optional	
finishing strategy	free text	optional	
annotation source	free text	optional	
sample volume or weight for DNA extraction	restricted text	optional	mL,g,mg,ng
nucleic acid extraction	free text	optional	
nucleic acid amplification	free text	optional	
library size	restricted text	optional	
library reads sequenced	restricted text	optional	
library construction method	free text	optional	
library vector	free text	optional	
library screening strategy	free text	optional	
target gene	free text	optional	
target subfragment	free text	optional	
pcr primers	free text	optional	
multiplex identifiers	free text	optional	
adapters	free text	optional	
pcr conditions	free text	optional	
sequencing method	free text	mandatory	
sequence quality check	text choice	optional	
chimera check	free text	optional	
relevant electronic resources	free text	optional	
relevant standard operating procedures	free text	optional	
investigation type	text choice	mandatory	
collection date	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (altitude)	restricted text	optional	m
geographic location (country and/or sea)	text choice	mandatory	
geographic location (latitude)	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location	restricted text	mandatory	

(longitude)			
geographic location (region and locality)	free text	optional	
host-associated environmental package	text choice	mandatory	
geographic location (depth)	restricted text	optional	m
environment (biome)	free text	mandatory	
environment (feature)	free text	mandatory	
environment (material)	free text	mandatory	
geographic location (elevation)	restricted text	optional	m
source material identifiers	free text	optional	
sample collection device or method	free text	optional	
sample material processing	free text	optional	
isolation and growth condition	free text	optional	
propagation	free text	optional	
amount or size of sample collected	restricted text	optional	L,g,kg,m ² ,m ³
host body product	free text	optional	
host dry mass	restricted text	optional	kg,g,mg
oxygenation status of sample	text choice	optional	
organism count	free text	optional	
sample storage duration	restricted text	optional	hr,day,wk,mth,yr
sample storage temperature	restricted text	optional	°C
sample storage location	free text	optional	
host disease status	free text	optional	
host common name	free text	optional	
host subject id	free text	optional	
host age	restricted text	optional	s,m,hr,dy,mth,yr,dec,cent
host taxid	restricted text	optional	
host body habitat	free text	optional	
host body site	free text	optional	
host life stage	free text	optional	
host height	restricted text	optional	mm,cm,m
host length	restricted text	optional	mm,cm,m
host growth conditions	free text	optional	
host substrate	free text	optional	
host total mass	restricted text	optional	g,kg
host infra-specific name	free text	optional	
host infra-specific rank	free text	optional	

host phenotype	free text	optional	
host body temperature	restricted text	optional	°C
host color	free text	optional	
host shape	free text	optional	
host sex	text choice	optional	
temperature	restricted text	optional	°C
sample salinity	restricted text	optional	psu
miscellaneous parameter	free text	optional	
host blood pressure diastolic	restricted text	optional	mm Hg
host blood pressure systolic	restricted text	optional	mm Hg
host diet	free text	optional	
host last meal	free text	optional	
host family relationship	free text	optional	
host genotype	free text	optional	
gravity	free text	optional	
subspecific genetic lineage	free text	optional	
trophic level	text choice	optional	
relationship to oxygen	text choice	optional	
known pathogenicity	free text	optional	
encoded traits	free text	optional	
observed biotic relationship	text choice	optional	
chemical administration	free text	optional	
perturbation	free text	optional	

5.6 Table 1F: ENA Checklist - GSC MixS plant associated (ERC000020)

Field Name	Field Format	Requirement	Units
project name	free text	mandatory	
experimental factor	free text	optional	
ploidy	free text	optional	
number of replicons	restricted text	optional	
extrachromosomal elements	restricted text	optional	
estimated size	restricted text	optional	
reference for biomaterial	free text	optional	
finishing strategy	free text	optional	
annotation source	free text	optional	
sample volume or weight for DNA extraction	restricted text	optional	mL,g,mg,ng
nucleic acid extraction	free text	optional	
nucleic acid amplification	free text	optional	
library size	restricted text	optional	
library reads sequenced	restricted text	optional	
library construction method	free text	optional	
library vector	free text	optional	
library screening strategy	free text	optional	
target gene	free text	optional	
target subfragment	free text	optional	
pcr primers	free text	optional	
multiplex identifiers	free text	optional	
adapters	free text	optional	
pcr conditions	free text	optional	
sequencing method	free text	mandatory	
sequence quality check	text choice	optional	
chimera check	free text	optional	
relevant electronic resources	free text	optional	
relevant standard operating procedures	free text	optional	
investigation type	text choice	mandatory	
collection date	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (altitude)	restricted text	optional	m
geographic location (country and/or sea)	text choice	mandatory	
geographic location (latitude)	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (longitude)	restricted text	mandatory	
geographic location (region and locality)	free text	optional	
plant-associated	text choice	mandatory	

environmental package			
geographic location (depth)	restricted text	optional	m
environment (biome)	free text	mandatory	
environment (feature)	free text	mandatory	
environment (material)	free text	mandatory	
geographic location (elevation)	restricted text	optional	m
source material identifiers	free text	optional	
sample collection device or method	free text	optional	
sample material processing	free text	optional	
isolation and growth condition	free text	optional	
propagation	free text	optional	
amount or size of sample collected	restricted text	optional	L,g,kg,m ² ,m ³
host dry mass	restricted text	optional	kg,g,mg
oxygenation status of sample	text choice	optional	
plant product	free text	optional	
organism count	free text	optional	
sample storage duration	restricted text	optional	
sample storage temperature	restricted text	optional	°C
host wet mass	restricted text	optional	
sample storage location	free text	optional	
host disease status	free text	optional	
host common name	free text	optional	
host age	restricted text	optional	s,m,hr,dy,mth,yr,dec,cent
host taxid	restricted text	optional	
host life stage	free text	optional	
host height	restricted text	optional	mm,cm,m
host length	restricted text	optional	mm,cm,m
plant body site	free text	optional	
host total mass	restricted text	optional	g,kg
host infra-specific name	free text	optional	
host infra-specific rank	free text	optional	
host phenotype	free text	optional	
climate environment	free text	optional	
gaseous environment	free text	optional	
seasonal environment	free text	optional	
temperature	restricted text	optional	°C
sample salinity	restricted text	optional	psu
miscellaneous parameter	free text	optional	
host genotype	free text	optional	
subspecific genetic lineage	free text	optional	
trophic level	text choice	optional	
relationship to oxygen	text choice	optional	

known pathogenicity	free text	optional	
encoded traits	free text	optional	
observed biotic relationship	text choice	optional	
air temperature regimen	free text	optional	
antibiotic regimen	free text	optional	
chemical mutagen	free text	optional	
fertilizer regimen	free text	optional	
fungicide regimen	free text	optional	
gravity	free text	optional	
growth hormone regimen	free text	optional	
growth media	free text	optional	
herbicide regimen	free text	optional	
humidity regimen	free text	optional	
mineral nutrient regimen	free text	optional	
non-mineral nutrient regimen	free text	optional	
pesticide regimen	free text	optional	
pH regimen	free text	optional	
radiation regimen	free text	optional	
rainfall regimen	free text	optional	
salt regimen	free text	optional	
standing water regimen	free text	optional	
tissue culture growth media	free text	optional	
watering regimen	free text	optional	
water temperature regimen	free text	optional	
mechanical damage	free text	optional	
chemical administration	free text	optional	
perturbation	free text	optional	

5.7 Table 2A: ISA Configuration - Genome Sequencing

Field Name	Field Format	Possible Values	Requirement
Measurement	term	genome sequencing	Mandatory
Technology	term	nucleotide sequencing (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000626)	Mandatory
Sample Name	free text		Mandatory
Nucleic acid Extraction Protocol	protocol		Optional
Extract Name	free text		Mandatory
Library Construction Protocol	protocol		Optional
Library Strategy	text choice	Amplicon, Other	Optional
Library Selection	text choice	PCR, Random-PCR, Restriction Digest, Size fractionation, Other	Optional
Library Layout	text choice	Single, Paired	Optional
Multiplex Identifier	restricted text		Optional
Sequencing Instrument	text choice	454 GS, Illumina HiSeq 2500, Illumina MiSeq etc	Optional
Base Caller	free text		Optional
Quality Scorer	free text		Optional
Assay Name	free text		Mandatory
Raw Data File	file		Mandatory
Normalization Name	free text		Optional
Data Transformation Name	free text		Optional
Derived Data File	file		Optional

5.8 Table 2B: ISA Configuration – Metagenome Sequencing

Field Name	Field Format	Possible Values	Requirement
Measurement	term	metagenome sequencing	Mandatory
Technology	term	nucleotide sequencing (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000626)	Mandatory
Sample Name	free text	Mandatory	
Nucleic acid Extraction Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Extract Name	free text	Mandatory	
Library Construction Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Library Strategy	text choice	Amplicon, Other	Optional
Library Selection	text choice	PCR, Random-PCR, Restriction Digest, Size fractionation, Other	Optional
Library Layout	text choice	Single, Paired	Optional
Multiplex Identifier	restricted text	Optional	
Sequencing Instrument	text choice	454 GS, Illumina HiSeq 2500, Illumina MiSeq etc	Optional
Base Caller	free text	Optional	
Quality Scorer	free text	Optional	
Assay Name	free text	Mandatory	
Raw Data File	file	Mandatory	
Normalization Name	free text	Optional	
Data Transformation Name	free text	Optional	
Derived Data File	file	Optional	

5.9 Table 2C: ISA Configuration – Transcriptome Sequencing

Field Name	Field Format	Possible Values	Requirement
Measurement	term	transcription profiling (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000424)	Mandatory
Technology	term	nucleotide sequencing (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000626)	Mandatory
Sample Name	free text	Mandatory	
Nucleic acid Extraction Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Extract Name	free text	Mandatory	
Library Construction Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Library Strategy	text choice	Amplicon, Other	Optional
Library Selection	text choice	PCR, Random-PCR, Restriction Digest, Size fractionation, Other	Optional
Library Layout	text choice	Single, Paired	Optional
Multiplex Identifier	restricted text	Optional	
Sequencing Instrument	text choice	454 GS, Illumina HiSeq 2500, Illumina MiSeq etc	Optional
Base Caller	free text	Optional	
Quality Scorer	free text	Optional	
Assay Name	free text	Mandatory	
Raw Data File	file	Mandatory	
Normalization Name	free text	Optional	
Data Transformation Name	free text	Optional	
Derived Data File	file	Optional	

5.10 Table 2D: ISA Configuration – DNA Methylation Sequencing

Field Name	Field Format	Possible Values	Requirement
Measurement	term	DNA methylation profiling (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000634)	Mandatory
Technology	term	nucleotide sequencing (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000626)	Mandatory
Sample Name	free text	Mandatory	
Nucleic acid Extraction Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Cross Linking	text choice	uv-light, formaldehyde, di-tert-butyl peroxide	Optional
DNA fragmentation	text choice	sonication, nebulization, nuclease digestion	Optional
DNA fragment size	restricted text	Optional	
Immunoprecipitation antibody	free text	Optional	
Extract Name	free text	Mandatory	
Library Construction Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Library Strategy	text choice	Amplicon, Other	Optional
Library Selection	text choice	PCR, Random-PCR, Restriction Digest, Size fractionation, Other	Optional
Library Layout	text choice	Single, Paired	Optional
Multiplex Identifier	restricted text	Optional	
Sequencing Instrument	text choice	454 GS, Illumina HiSeq 2500, Illumina MiSeq etc	Optional
Base Caller	free text	Optional	
Quality Scorer	free text	Optional	
Assay Name	free text	Mandatory	
Raw Data File	file	Mandatory	
Sequence Analysis Data Transformation protocol	Optional		
Normalization Name	free text	Optional	
Data Transformation Name	free text	Optional	
Derived Data File	file	Optional	

5.11 Table 2E: ISA Configuration – Proteomics Profiling

Field Name	Field Format	Possible Values	Requirement
Measurement	term	protein expression profiling (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000615)	Mandatory
Technology	term	mass spectrometry (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000470)	Mandatory
Sample Name	free text	Mandatory	
Extraction Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Extract Name	free text	Mandatory	
Labelling Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Label	term	CHEBI	Optional
Mass Spectrometry Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Instrument	term	Instrument Model (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000031)	Optional
Ion source	term	Ion Source (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000458)	Optional
Detector	term	Detector (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000453)	Optional
Analyzer	term	Mass Analyzer (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000451)	Optional
MS Assay Name	free text	Mandatory	
Raw Spectral Data File	file	Mandatory	
Data Transformation	protocol	Optional	
Normalization Name	free text	Optional	
Data Transformation Name	free text	Optional	
Derived Spectral Data File	file	Optional	
Peptide Assignment File	file	Optional	
Protein Assignment File	file	Optional	
Post Translational Assignment File	file	Optional	

5.12 Table 2F: ISA Configuration – Mass Spectrometry based Metabolomics

Field Name	Field Format	Possible Values	Requirement
Measurement	term	metabolite profiling (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000366)	Mandatory
Technology	term	mass spectrometry (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000470)	Mandatory
Sample Name	free text	Mandatory	
Extraction Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Extract Name	free text	Mandatory	
Labelling Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Label	term	CHEBI	Optional
Mass Spectrometry Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Instrument	term	Instrument Model (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000031)	Optional
Ion source	term	Ion Source (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000458)	Optional
Detector	term	Detector (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000453)	Optional
Analyzer	term	Mass Analyzer (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MS_1000451)	Optional
MS Assay Name	free text	Mandatory	
Raw Spectral Data File	file	Mandatory	
Data Transformation	protocol	Optional	
Normalization Name	free text	Optional	
Data Transformation Name	free text	Optional	
Derived Spectral Data File	file	Optional	
Metabolite Assignment File	file	Optional	

5.13 Table 2G: ISA Configuration – Nuclear Magnetic Resonance based Metabolomics

Field Name	Field Format	Possible Values	Requirement
Measurement	term	metabolite profiling (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000366)	Mandatory
Technology	term	NMR spectroscopy (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000623)	Mandatory
Sample Name	free text	Mandatory	
Extraction Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Extract Name	free text	Mandatory	
Labelling Protocol	protocol	Optional	
Label	term	CHEBI	Optional
NMR Spectrometry Protocol	protocol	Optional	
NMR Probe	free text	Optional	
Number of acquisition	free text	Optional	
Magnetic field strength	free text	Optional	
Acquisition Parameter Data File	file	Optional	
NMR Assay Name	free text	Mandatory	
Free Induction Decay Data File	file	Optional	
Data Transformation	protocol	Optional	
Normalization Name	free text	Optional	
Data Transformation Name	free text	Optional	
Derived Spectral Data File	file	Optional	
Metabolite Assignment File	file	Optional	

ⁱ <https://fairsharing.org/collection/MIBBI>